

PINE, YEW AND FIR IN MEDIEVAL WELSH SOURCES

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the characterisation of three conifers: *yw* (yew), *pinus* (pine) and *ffynidwydd* ('fir' in the broadest sense) in Middle Welsh sources, as well as the status of these trees in medieval Wales. Pine was likely extremely rare in Wales during the medieval period, but there is some evidence possibly referring to its presence in medieval texts. Yew was declining but more common, both as a naturally occurring species and as individual trees planted in churchyards and abbeys and beside holy wells. Yew gained a reputation for holiness based on these holy trees, and pine gained a separate reputation for holiness based on its appearance in the legend of the rood. All the conifers also seem to have acquired reputations as disruptive, liminal species and may have been included in texts as a sign to the reader that the ordinary rules of the secondary world had been suspended.

... ac a oed las o wisg y marchawc a'e uarch a oed kyn lasset a deil y ffenitwyd, ac a oed velyn ohonei a oed kyn uelynet a blodeu y banadyl. (Richards 1948: 4)

'And that which was green of the outfit of the knight and his horse was as green as the needles of fir trees, and that which was yellow of it was as yellow as the flowers of broom.' (my translation)

THE QUOTATION ABOVE IS TAKEN from the description of Iddog Cordd Prydain near the beginning of *Breuddwyd Rhonabwy* ('The Dream of Rhonabwy'). The mention of the fir trees here raises questions. Unlike broom, which is a native shrub, fir trees are not native to Britain, and were not commonly grown in Wales during the medieval period, so how did fir gain the cultural currency to be mentioned in a text like *Breuddwyd Rhonabwy*? Would it make a difference if *ffenitwyd* was instead translated as 'pine'? What made the specific shade of green of the fir tree the most suitable comparison for a knight's green outfit? And why is this knight dressed in green at all, when no other character in any of the stories familiarly known nowadays as the *Mabinogion* seems to wear the colour?

There are three main conifers which are commonly mentioned in Middle Welsh sources. These are *yw* (singulative *ywen*), the yew tree; *pinus*, the pine tree; and *ffynidwydd* (singulative *ffynidwydden*), meaning either the fir or pine tree. The purpose of this paper is to explore how each of these three trees was

characterised in medieval Welsh sources. To begin, it is worth exploring the status that conifers in general had in medieval Wales.

MEDIEVAL STATUS OF CONIFERS IN WALES

There are three conifers which are native to Britain and Ireland, and these make a useful starting point for our discussion. Confusingly however, the three native species are not all the same as the three conifers most commonly mentioned in medieval Welsh sources. The native species are the Common Yew (*Taxus baccata* L.), the Scots Pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.), but also the Common Juniper (*Juniperus communis* L.). Of these, the medieval Welsh sources have very little to say about juniper. It is almost absent from pre-1500 Welsh sources, except in the form of Savin Juniper (a Mediterranean species, *Juniperus sabina* L., imported as medicine), included in the list of plant names in BL Additional MS 14912 (Stokes 1900; Luft 2020: 240–1, 502).

Yw (Common Yews) were associated with churchyards, abbeys and holy wells in medieval Britain, Ireland, and northern France, where they appear to have been widely planted in the early medieval period (Bevan-Jones 2016: 28–30). This led to the yew having a prestigious reputation in medieval Wales. This can be judged fairly objectively by consulting the legal value of yew in the medieval Welsh law codes. An ordinary yew tree found in the woods (*ywen coet/taxus*) was valued at 15d. under the *Blegywryd*, *Cyfnernth*, and Latin C and D law codes and 30d. in *Iorwerth* C (Jenkins 1986: 188–9; Roberts 2011: 125; Wiliam 1960: 91; Owen 1841: 584–5, 724–7 (GC II.xviii.66–7; DC II.xxxv.86–7); Emanuel 1967: 290, 364). This places yew ordinarily at an intermediate legal value among trees. A yew tree was given a legal value which was less than that of the highest-valued timber and fruit trees (oak, beech and cultivated apple trees), and about the same as a fruiting crab apple or a hazel. It was valued above other trees which do not produce fruit, like ash or alder or willow (cf. Linnard 1976). This also fits with its appearance as a boundary marker alongside alder, apple, ash, broom and willow in the Book of Llandaff (NLW MS 17110E) (Linnard 2000: 120; Evans and Rhys 1893: 372). However, under the *Cyfnernth*, *Blegywryd* and Latin D law codes, a holy or saint's yew (*ywen sant/taxus sancta*) had a separate legal value. This was twenty shillings or one pound, which is double the value of an oak tree, otherwise the highest-valued of all the trees (Jenkins 1986: 188–9; Roberts 2011: 125; Owen 1841: 584–5, 724–7 (GC II.xviii.66–7; DC II.xxxv.86–7); Emanuel 1967: 364). Holy yew trees were highly valued and more strictly protected than ordinary woodland yews. This was fortunate because, outside of the holy sites, yews were extensively felled across medieval Europe to meet the demand for longbows. Yew was especially suitable for making longbows because the inner heartwood is stronger and the outer sapwood can flex, so a bow which incorporated both kinds of wood could be very powerful. These two types of wood were distinguished in the seventeenth century vocabulary of John Jones of Gellilyfdy as *gwnning uw* ('yew sapwood') and *rhudding uw* ('yew heartwood') (Parry Owen 2023: 121.195–9). By this point though, the supply of accessible, mature yew trees appears to

have been close to depleted (Hageneder 2013: 103–4, 107–113; Bevan-Jones 2016: 144). Signs of high demand for yew bows are seen in medieval Wales in the poems begging bows from rich patrons, like the fifteenth-century *I ofyn bwa gan Ddafydd Llwyd ap Gruffudd* ('To ask for a bow from Dafydd Llwyd ap Gruffudd'), a poem by Lewys Glyn Cothi that asks for a yew bow the colour of fire and snow with pine terminals (Johnston 1995: 211.35–42; Linnard 2000: 459–60). The decline of Europe's yew stocks may even have eventually inspired the movement to shotguns in the sixteenth century. Since the 1960s, cancer treatments have been developed from yew trees, including taxol (from the bark) and Taxotere (from the needle-like leaves). This has inspired further felling of yew trees across America, Asia and eastern Europe. The yew trees still protected in British churchyards now have a new significance as one of the main reservoirs of veteran and ancient yews remaining in the world (Hageneder 2013: Chapter 11).

Pinus (Scots Pine) is another native tree, but one which was almost extinct in Wales by the medieval period. Around 9,000 years ago, shortly after the end of the last glacial period, Scots Pine re-colonised Britain and it spread to its maximum extent over the next 4,500 years (Bennett 1984; Kinloch, Westfall and Forrest 1986; McGeever and Mitchell 2016). But around 4,000 years ago it began to decline, and was soon lost from most of its former range in Britain and Ireland outside of the Scottish Highlands. Small, isolated populations survived in some locations: a piece of carbonised (burnt) pine was found at Bryn Celli Ddu on Anglesey, dating from 1500 BCE, suggesting that pine might have been available locally then (Linnard 2000: 10). A supply seems to have still been available during the medieval period in some areas, as for example in Borth in Ceredigion, where fossilised pine wood in the nearby peat bog has been dated to the early medieval period (Harkness and Wilson 1979; Bennett 1984; Hyde 1961: 59). The most interesting survivals outside of Highland Scotland are at Rockforest in the Burren, co. Clare; at Kielder Forest in Northumberland, north England; and at Lin Can Moss in the Welsh Marches (McGeever and Mitchell 2016; Manning et al. 2010; Sassoon et al. 2021), where pine populations appear to have survived all the way through to the present day. Outside of these isolated locations, pine was likely extinct, and was only commonly imported and re-introduced onto estates and plantations in Wales after the end of the medieval period along with non-native species like Silver Fir (*Abies alba*), from the mid-seventeenth century onwards (Linnard 2000: 79, 131; Hyde 1961: 59). Pine trees in medieval Britain tended to grow in marginal soils in upland areas, and they do not grow well in the shadow of other pine trees (Mason 2013: 39). There are also a few tentative records of Welsh pine trees in historical sources. The reference by George Owen of Henllys in his *Description of Pembrokeshire* (1603) to 'divers rare timber, as the pineapple tree, the spruce and fir trees, the mulberry tree and others' (ed. Miles 1994: 146–7), growing around husbandmen's houses, seems to refer to very early planting of specimen trees. A more plausible record of native pine is from Nehemiah Grew's unpublished text of 1706–7, *England's Economic Development*, which recommended planting

pinus more widely in Britain, since there were already successful pine plantations in some estates, and ‘the worst Land in Wales is said to bear large Pines’ (Hopfit 2012: 28). The term ‘the worst land’ suggests that these last pines were not planted on farms or stately homes, so this might indicate a relict population, although of course it could equally represent early plantation by an enterprising upland landowner. In medieval Welsh sources, the most plausible record is in the reciter’s prologue to *Y Gododdin*, which describes Aneurin in front of a fire *O lychwr i lychwr lluch bin* (Williams 1938: 55A), ‘The pine logs blazing from dusk to dawn’ (Jarman 1988: 3 (55A)). This is a strong piece of evidence because, whilst pine furniture and artwork might have been imported from Scotland or the Continent, where pine trees were more common, firewood would have been obtained locally. This means that if the idea of burning pine on fires was not poetic licence, there must have been a domestic source of pine-wood in the medieval period. There are, however, two possible criticisms of this source (Linnard 2000: 10). First, since *Y Gododdin* may possibly originate in what is now southern Scotland or northern England, this text might not be a suitable source for the existence of pine trees in medieval Wales. In answer to this first point, it is worth noting that this particular verse has two forms. The only form which mentions pine is the younger A-text of *Y Gododdin*, so its claim to medieval Welsh provenance is stronger than other parts of the text. Linnard’s second criticism is to point out that pine firewood might have been obtained from the fossilised remains of much older pine trees salvaged from peat bogs. Fossilised wood has been regularly found and recognised as pine in the modern period, so it is conceivable that it might have been known and used in the medieval period too. These two criticisms mean that the evidence of *Y Gododdin* does not necessarily reflect a relict population of pine in medieval Wales, but as we shall see, other records of Scots Pine might also be included under other Welsh terms.

The third main conifer term in medieval Welsh is *ffynidwydd* (singulative: *ffynidwydden*, meaning ‘fir’, but also sometimes ‘pine’). The medieval distinction between *ffynidwydd* and *pinus* has parallels in other neighbouring languages, as for example medieval Latin *abies* and *pinus*, Middle English *firre* and *pynus*, and Old French *sap* and *pin*. There is now a strict division between the terms *pine* (scientific genus: *Pinus*) and *fir* (scientific genus: *Abies*), but the medieval division between these terms was not scientific but cultural. It might be an appropriate analogue to think of the difference between these species as being like the difference between the medieval *Bestiary* ‘panther’ and ‘pard’. Both these terms appear to have been originally names for the Leopard (*Panthera pardus*) but in practice they had acquired different cultural characterisations by the medieval period (Barber 2006: 30–5). In the past, the term *fir* was regularly used to describe the Scots Pine. John Parkinson, who was the first botanist to officially describe the native Scots Pine trees of Highland Scotland, called them *abies* and *fir* (Pearman 2017: 309; Parkinson 1640: 1540). Robert Sibbald (1684: 6 (II:1)), writing half a century later, used the same terms for the trees of Highland Scotland, and even attempted to distinguish these from the true *picea* (pine?) trees, which he believed should

have bigger cones. This confusion is also seen in Wales. In the eighteenth century, when conifers like Silver Fir began to be more widely planted, one of the most common kinds of ‘fir’ planted on estates in Wales was ‘Scotch fir’, again meaning *Pinus sylvestris*, the modern Scots Pine (Linnard 2000: 132–5). Some medieval texts also use the term *ffynidwydd* in a context which implies that they might be talking about Scots Pine. In *Cad Goddeu* (traditionally translated as ‘The Battle of the Trees’), one of the poems associated with the legendary Taliesin in the fourteenth-century Book of Taliesin (NLW Peniarth MS 2), Gwydion, at the instruction of God, calls a long list of trees, shrubs and herbaceous plants to take part in a battle. Each tree is named and given a mock-heroic description (Haycock 1990; 2007: poem 5). *Pinus* and *yw* are not mentioned but *ffynidwydd* is one of the trees named in the text: *Ffenitwyd yg kynted / Kadeir gygrwyssed* (‘[Fir] in the place of honour / Contention in the shape of branches’ (Haycock 2007: 5.98–9)). The translation here is obscure, but the inclusion of *ffynidwydd* at all is important because almost every identifiable plant mentioned in this poem is native and would have been found in Wales. There are five other exceptions which are not native, but all can be much more easily explained. Sweet Chestnut, Medlar, Woad and Pears are all archaeophytes: they are not native but had already been introduced to Wales as garden or wild plants (Preston, Pearman and Dines 2002: 130, 252, 371, 357). The fifth exception, Beech, had a limited native distribution in Britain. It was absent from much of medieval Wales, but it seems to be native to south-east England and south-east Wales, where it does seem to have been present in the medieval period (Linnard 2000: 9; Preston, Pearman and Dines 2002: 129). If the term *ffynidwydd* here was supposed to refer to what we now think of as a true fir tree like the Silver Fir (*Abies alba*), it would be the only species in the list which was not present in medieval Wales. For this reason, it makes more sense to translate the term here as ‘pine’, as Haycock (2007: 5.98) indeed does, since although Scots Pine trees had become exceptionally rare in medieval Wales, there do still seem to have been some growing here, as explained above.

There are also other terms which are used more rarely in Welsh literature, but which might also indicate conifers. The term *fyr* starts to appear in Welsh poetry in the second half of the fifteenth century, and is used in elegies and praise poetry by both northern and southern poets. It is glossed with the Latin *abies* (fir) in John Davies’ seventeenth-century *Dictionarium Duplex* (ed. Alston 1968) and it may be a borrowing from English *firre/vyrre* (fir). Almost all of the fifteenth century records of the term use it to refer to spears, lances and javelins (Foster Evans 2000: 3.4; Johnston 1995: 164.6; Lake 2015: 13.16; Roberts and Williams 1923: 8.58, 20.68; Williams and Rowlands 1976: 23.15). The existence of these weapons does not necessarily indicate a native population of conifers since they could have been imported along with the word used to describe their material. Further, even if the weapons were made of local wood, Roberts and Williams (1923: 171 n. 68) suggest that the form *prenfyr* could even

be taken as a plural form of **prenfwrw* ('throwing wood').¹ This translation would remove any hint of conifers from the texts. However, in the fifteenth-century *Marwnad Tomas ap Trahaearn ap Gwilym* by Hywel Dafi, the term *fyr* seems to be attached to an actual living population of trees: 'Yn Llan-faes dan y llwyn fyr / Gwnaeth nef iddo dref a drig' (Lake 2015: 36.46–7 – 'In Llanfaes under the fir grove / Heaven made a homestead for him that will endure' – my translation). This does not refer to throwing weapons, either imported or local. It could refer to exceptionally early planting of specimen conifer trees on a private estate, as we saw from the later *Description of Pembrokeshire*, or conceivably to a late relict population of Scots Pine near Brecon. Similarly, *GPC* notes that the term *fer* is also attested in the placename *Pant-y-fer*. There were five places called *Pant-y-fer* in Carmarthenshire on the *GB1900 Ordnance Survey Map* (RCAHMW 2023). All but one of these are included on all Ordnance Survey Maps from the first map in the 1880s until the 1960s, before being no longer recorded from the 1970s onwards (the last disappears earlier). It seems likely that these places were named after eighteenth- or nineteenth-century forestry plantations, some of which are still present today, although the *Pant-y-fer* at National Grid Reference SN 54155 33334 lay within the Brechfa Forest, an area of ancient woodland, so might merit further investigation.

Another much earlier, dubious reference to pine is in *Eiry Mynydd* ('Mountain Snow'), one of the anonymous, possibly eleventh- or twelfth-century, quasi-gnomic poems included in the Red Book of Hergest (Oxford, Jesus College MS 111) as well as Oxford, Jesus College MS 20. In each *englyn*, the first line or the first two lines describe the setting of a winter's day in the mountains, presumably in Wales, whilst the last gives a truism about the human condition. Once again, all the species mentioned are those which would have been actually present within this setting, except perhaps that dock leaves are described here, which are not usually visible in winter. One of the *englynion* runs:

Eiry mynyd; coch blaen pyr;
Llidiawc lluossawc ongyr;
Och, rac hiraeth vy mrodyr!
(Jacobs 2012: 2.21)

'Mountain snow, fir-top red.
Spear-thrusts fierce, frequent
Ah, my brothers, the yearning.'
(Clancy 2003: 113)

The contents of this stanza have suggested to Jacobs (2012: 39) that it might belong to a saga and therefore be earlier than the rest of the poem. The word translated as 'fir' here is *pyr*, which normally means 'pear trees' (Jacobs 2012: 125). Clancy's translation 'fir' seems to be based on Pughe's (1803) dictionary

¹Although in context, their translation seems unlikely since the previous line (20.67) refers to two other species of tree (beech and ash) that Wiliam Fychan can easily break.

which defines *pyr* as a fir tree, possibly as a result of taking *phyr* as an aspirated form and extrapolating a basic form *pyr*. A conifer might also fit better into the setting of the poem, and conifers do sometimes struggle and show signs of stress (like reddening) when exposed to cold dry winds and extreme cold and frost (Hageneder 2013: 21). If this reading is accepted it could represent another medieval Welsh depiction of the Scots Pine growing in a native setting, but this reference is dubious because the word *pyr* is not attested elsewhere in the literature with the meaning ‘fir’ rather than ‘pear’.

HOLINESS

Pine trees had a reputation for holiness across Europe, because of the influence of the legend of the rood. In Wales, this legend was most famously transmitted in the Middle Welsh *Ystorya Adaf* (‘The History of Adam’), which is a translation of the Latin *Historia Adam*. The part of the story which deals with the pine starts with how an angel gave Seth the son of Adam three pips from an apple from Paradise. He was told to plant these pips under the tongue of Adam, after Adam had died. Three conifers grew from the pips, one of which was a pine tree:

Ac onadunt ykyuodant teir gŵialen. Vn onadunt avyd oryŵ cedrus yr eil a vyd o ryŵ cypressus. Ar tryded auyd oryŵ ypinus. Trwy ycedrus ydeallir ytat or nef. Kannys vchaf prenn ydyfyant yŵ. Drŵy cypressus y deallir ymab. Kanyŵ goreu prenn yŵ y arogleu amelyssaf yffrŵyth. Trŵy ypinus ydeallir yrysbryt glan herŵyð amylder yffrŵyth. (Jenkins 1921: 124)

‘And from these pips will arise three shoots. One of them will be of cedar kind, one of them will be of cypress kind, and the third will be of pine kind. Through the cedar is understood the Father of Heaven, because it is the highest-growing tree. Through cypress is understood the Son because it is the tree whose aroma is best and whose fruit is sweetest. Through the pine is understood the Holy Spirit because of the large amount of its fruit.’ (my translation)

The rods that grew from these three shoots were responsible for various miracles, before ultimately joining together to become the wood used to make the cross on which Jesus was crucified. The same story about the three holy conifers is told in various texts across medieval Europe, for example, a very closely related version of the story in the fourteenth-century Middle English *Cursor Mundi*: *þai sal be cedre, ciprese, and pine / O þam sal man haue medicen* (Morris 1874: ll. 1366–86) (‘They shall be cedar, cypress and pine / From them humans will have medicine’). Another allusion to this story is in the *Awdl i’r Grog o Gaer* written by the fourteenth-century poet Gruffudd ap Maredudd:

Rhadlawn ddawn a ddoeth, Rhi Tri trichyfoeth,
 I loyw Gaer goeth o fro Loegr gain
 Rhywogaeth cedrus, rhwydd swydd cypressus,
 O geingiau pinus a rygyngain
 (Lewis 2005a: ll. 163–6)

‘A gift full of grace has come, the threefold King of three kingdoms
 To bright, fair Chester of the realm of fine England:
 The species of cedar, cypress which performs its function smoothly,²
 Of branches of pine which intertwine together.’
 (Lewis, 2005b: 39 (ll. 163–6))

This poem combines imagery describing the Rood of Chester, the original True Cross, and Christ himself (Lewis 2005b: 8). The section quoted above appears to describe both the Rood of Chester and the construction of the True Cross from cedar, cypress and pine. Cedar and cypress are rarely found elsewhere in medieval Welsh literature, but there are also allusions just to pine as one of the materials of the cross, as for example in the fourteenth-century *Awdl i Iesu Grist* possibly written by Dafydd ap Gwilym, which explains how Jesus went *I brynu penydd ar bren pinus* (‘to buy redemption on a pine tree’) (Lake et al. 2007: 152.26). This reputation may also explain the fifteenth-century reference in Lewys Glyn Cothi’s *Marwnad dau fab Phylib ap Rhys* (‘Elegy for the two sons of Phylib ap Rhys’), where one of the two sons is described as being *haelaf, pennaf fal pren pinys* (Johnston 1995: 189.16–18) (‘the most generous, a chieftain like a pine tree’).

Yew trees also had a comparable reputation for holiness because, as previously explained, they were commonly planted in churchyards and abbeys and besides holy wells (Bevan-Jones 2016: 28–30). In these situations, holy yew trees have the highest legal values of all trees in the medieval Welsh law codes. Yew trees in churchyards have also traditionally had a ritual use. Branches and sprigs have traditionally been taken from yew trees for Palm Sunday and Ash Wednesday celebrations in Britain for use in lieu of palm leaves, as noted for example in the fourteenth-century *Festial* of John Mirk of Shropshire (Erbe 1905: 115). As well as in Britain, yew trees were clearly also important in Ireland (Mac Coitir 2016). Gerald of Wales, writing in a later addition to his *Topography of Ireland* of 1188, notes that yew trees were common in Ireland in ancient graveyards and holy places (Dimock 1867: 152). *The Annals of the Four Masters* records the burning of yews in churchyards at *Gleann-Uiscan* (Killeshin in Co. Laois) in 1077, and *Iubhar-Chinntrechta* (Newry) in 1162 (O’Donovan 1856: 1146–7), a name that contains the Irish word for yew, *iubhar*, see p. 100 below. The *Annals of Tigernach* add that the yew tree of St Ciarán at Clonmacnoise was hit by lightning in 1149, supposedly killing 113 sheep sheltering underneath it (Mac Niocaill 2010: 170). A similar sentiment to that of Gerald of Wales is even expressed by Suibne, hero of the Irish tale *Buile Shuibne: A iubhair, a iubhracháin / I*

²Alternatively, ‘a smooth cypress seat’ (?), see Russell (2000: 282).

rei[l]gibh bat reil ('O yew-tree, little yew tree / in churchyards thou art conspicuous') (O'Keefe 1910: 66–7).

The yew tree's holy reputation in Britain and Ireland is consistent with the classical tradition of venerating groves at religious sites. However, the sacred groves associated with the druids of northern Europe were mistrusted by Roman authors like Lucan and Tacitus who often depicted them as ancient and bloody sites of sacrifice, which are felled by brave Roman heroes (Jackson 1937, XIV.30; Duff 1928, III.399ff.). In Christian writing this distrust was sometimes extended to all pagan trees so that for example in the Life of St Martin of Tours, initially recorded in the fourth- or early fifth-century *Vita S. Martini* of Sulpicius Severus, St Martin has to fell an unholy pine tree outside a pagan temple. This story was further transmitted across medieval Europe as part of the *Golden Legend* (it is in vol. 6 of William Caxton's English edition (ed. Ellis: 1900)). St Martin was commonly venerated in Wales (Day 2017), and his life was translated as the *Buchedd Sant Martin* in 1488. The version of the story there introduces the tree quite simply: *prenn pinivis oedd yn emyl y demyl* ('a pine tree was beside the temple') and says that St Martin had to fell it *kanis ef a gysegrwyd y'r Kythrel* ('because it was consecrated to the Devil') (Day 2020: §20). This may have been especially easy to conceptualise by Welsh readers because of the presence of so many holy yew trees in Wales.

The most famous holy yew in medieval Welsh sources is of course the tree addressed in Gruffudd Gryg's fourteenth-century poem *I'r ywen uwchben bedd Dafydd ap Gwilym* ('To the yew tree above Dafydd ap Gwilym's Grave'). This poem is directed to a yew tree at Strata Florida Abbey, in the churchyard of St Mary's Church, where Gruffudd tells us that Dafydd ap Gwilym has been buried. There were once many yew trees at the Abbey, and John Leland (Smith 1906: 118) recorded that 39 yews still grew there in the sixteenth century, two of which still stand today. The poem starts by situating the reader, greeting the yew, and telling its story:

Yr ywen i oreuwas
 Ger mur Ystrad-fflur a'i phlas,
 Da Duw wrthyd, gwynfyd gwŷdd
 Dy dyfu yn dŷ Dafydd.
 Dafydd Llwyd a'th broffwydawdd
 Er cyn dy dyfu rhag cawdd;
 Dafydd, gwedi dy dyfu,
 A'th wnaeth, o'i fabolaeth fu
 Dy urddo, yn dŷ irddail,
 Tŷ a phob llwyn yn dwyn dail;
 Castell cudd meirw rhag eirwynt
 Cystal â'r pren gwial gynt;
 Dy leau bu deuluaidd,
 Dy wrysg, dy gangau, dy wraidd.
 (Salisbury in Lewis and Salisbury 2010: 5.1–14)

‘Yew for the best of lads
 Beside the wall of Ystrad-fflur [Strata Florida] and its palace.
 God’s blessing to you, paradise of trees
 For growing as Dafydd’s house.
 Dafydd Llwyd prophesied you
 Before you grew in the face of tribulation;
 Dafydd, after you grew,
 Honoured you – from his youth it was –
 As a house of green leaves,
 A house with every bough bearing leaves;
 A hidden castle for the dead against the snowy wind
 As good as the tree of rods of old;
 Your parts were noble,
 Your boughs your branches, your roots.’
 (Bollard and Griffiths 2019: 106–7)

This text has provoked a great deal of debate (best summarised in Bromwich, Parry and Bowen 1984) about whether it is a genuine elegy of homage or was intended as a humorous mock-elegy as part of the long *ymryson* (bardic dispute) between Dafydd ap Gwilym and Gruffudd Gryg. Addressing the debate would be outside of the scope of this paper but it is worth noting here that the poem presents a sophisticated depiction of a yew tree, with several extratextual references to other trees. For example, the wish that Dafydd’s yew will become like the *pren gwial gynt* (‘tree of rods of old’) seems to be a reference to the pine-cedar-cypress tree from the legend of the rood, previously described from *Ystorya Adaf* (Bollard and Griffiths 2019: 137–9; Lewis and Salisbury 2010: 146–50). Likewise, the description of the yew as a *dŷ irddail*, (house of green leaves) seems to be a reference to Dafydd ap Gwilym’s other poetry, where he compares his work to carpentry and praises woodland spaces which provide him with shelter for his trysts (Bromwich 1986: 161; Bromwich, Parry and Bowen 1984; Davies 2005; Bevan-Jones 2016: 58–80). This is not simply a yew tree, but a vehicle for all the trees in the fourteenth-century Welsh cultural imagination. Ultimately, though, even with the sophisticated ideas conveyed by this famous yew tree, the foundational concept of the poem is still that of the holy yew growing in the graveyard. The disagreement can be reduced to one of authorial intention: whether or not the solemn effect provided by the presence of the holy yew is being humorously undercut by the tone and the extratextual comparisons with other trees.

There is less evidence that *ffynidwydd* (fir trees) were considered to be holy. One antisemitic miracle story included in the thirteenth-century text *Gwyrthyeu y Wynvydedic Veir* (‘Miracles of the Blessed Mary’) in NLW MS Peniarth 14 does involve money being placed in a fir container with iron strips bound with pitch (Jones 1941: 28). However, the container is ultimately peripheral to the main miracle (Mary’s later intercession on behalf of the merchant), and the use of pitch was common in the past to waterproof containers and boats (Mason 2013: 72–4, 85–90). Perhaps a more convincing reference to fir being

holy is in the mystic text *Ymborth yr Enaid* ('Sustenance of the Soul'), a religious text from the Book of the Anchorite of Llanddewibrefi (Oxford, Jesus College MS 119), which was part of the *Cysegrlan Fuchedd* ('Holy Living'), most of which no longer survives (Daniel 1997). This text compares the love of Jesus to sweet kisses which shine like sparks arising from fir incense (Daniel 1995: 18–19). Interestingly, the *pinus* (pine) and *ywen* (yew) do not seem to have this same importance as aromatic woods in the medieval Welsh cultural imagination, but the reputation of *ffynidwydd* as an aromatic wood is also supported by Gerald of Wales, again in his *Topography of Ireland*. Alongside his remarks about yew trees, he also notes that, 'Item abundat et abiete silvositas Hiberniae, thuris et incensi matre.' (Dimock 1867: 152) ('Fir, the mother of incense and perfume, is also common in the wooded parts of Ireland.' (my translation)). The record here could be allegorical, as many of Gerald's later additions were (Bartlett 2006: 121–7), but if it is not, it could possibly be one of the last records of Ireland's remnant population of Scots Pine. Pine also appears in Irish historical sources, including being listed alongside yew in the most prestigious category of trees (*airig fedo*, the 'nobles of the wood') in the eighth-century *Bretha Comaithchesa* ('Judgements of Neighbourhood') (Charles-Edwards 2022: 154–5; Kelly 1976: 111–13), although it is sometimes left out of the later medieval literary tree lists which draw on this law, perhaps because it had by then become rare (Joseph and Drayton 2021). It is still listed as present in *Conkeinia* (Glencokeyne) in Philip O'Sullivan Beare's *Natural History of Ireland* of 1626 (ed. 2009: 200–1). The Old Irish saga *Táin Bó Fraích* (c. 750) refers to a royal abode being made of pine: *de giús dognúth a tech*; cf. Meid (1967: 3, ll. 69–70).

Apart from its aromatic importance, *ffynidwydd* ('fir') appears to have been considered a low-quality wood. In the fourteenth-century *Cywydd yr Halaenwr* ('The Saltman'), a short fabliau by Madog Benfras, the main character swaps places with a travelling salt-seller in order to infiltrate a mansion to meet with a lover. The main character sarcastically describes what a good deal he received for his well-trained horse by exaggerating the poor quality of the salt-seller's outfit. One item that the salt-seller had was a salt basket: *y cawell halen cywair / I'w ddwyn, o'r hengrwyn a'r hair / Ac erwydd ffynidwydd ffyn* (Lewis and Morys 2007: 5.17) ('The basket full of salt / to carry it, made of hairy old hide / and rods, twigs of fir' – translation after Lewis and Morys 2007: 5.15–17). This implies that *ffynidwydd* was considered a low-quality material, despite its aromatic properties. This of course fits with what we know of fir today: conifers like fir and pine are softwoods and have a much lower strength than hardwoods like oak, beech and ash, although yew is strong despite being a softwood (Mason 2013: 102; Linnard 2000: 112–3).

It also appears that none of the three conifers, including *ffynidwydd* ('fir'), were particularly noted to have medicinal properties in medieval Welsh sources. This is surprising, because pine and yew were both used in traditional medicine practices elsewhere in the world, as we previously found in the fourteenth-century *Cursor Mundi* (Hageneder 2013: 99–100; Mason 2013: 153–7). Another Middle English example is John Trevisa's translation of

Bartholomaeus Anglicus' *De Proprietatibus Rerum*. Here both pinecones and pitch made from pine resin are assigned several medicinal properties (Trevisa and Anglicus 1975: 1018–19). There is only one possible example of medicinal use from medieval Wales: an ingredient named *iawn* is included in a recipe for contraception and abortion in the medieval Welsh medical texts, and this could be an unusual spelling of *ywen* (Luft 2020: 102–3 (4/13), 320 n. 113). Yew has occasionally been tried through history as a medicine for abortions, but this does not seem to have been common in Britain (Hageneder 2013: 158). Medical interest in the conifers increased after the end of the medieval period in Wales. In the nineteenth century, the aromatic reputation of pine forests made them important sites for tuberculosis sanatoria, and pine scent became widely used in disinfectants, as it still is today (Hickman 2022).

COLOUR AND DISRUPTIVENESS

The conifers do not always come into medieval Welsh texts as actual trees or even wooden items. Sometimes they can have an effect on a text just by being referenced. Perhaps the most popular aspect of conifers for modern gardeners is their colour. As evergreens, conifers maintain a dense shape and green colour in the garden through the winter, when most other plants die down or lose their leaves. This aspect of the conifers was noted and valued in the medieval period too. In the aforementioned Middle English translation of Bartholomaeus Anglicus' *De Proprietatibus Rerum*, the text notes that pine *is grene boþe wynter and somer* ('is green both winter and summer') (Trevisa and Anglicus 1975: 1017–18). This is also commented on in Welsh literature. The clearest example of it is in *Ystorya Trystan*, a prosimetric Arthurian story combining a possibly early group of *englynion* with a later fabliau frame story, preserved in several manuscripts, the earliest of which is from the mid-sixteenth century (Rowland and Thomas 1982). In this story, Arthur is asked to judge whether Eyllt should be forced to stay with her husband March ap Meirchion, or be allowed to leave to pursue a relationship with Trystan. Arthur pronounces Persephone's fate: Eyllt should be with one of the men when there are leaves on the trees, and the other when the leaves are gone. March chooses to be with Eyllt when the leaves are gone, at which Eyllt triumphantly announces:

'Tri ffren sy dda i rryw
Kelyn ag eiddew ag yw
A ddeilan ddail yni byw
Trystan pie fi yni fyw.'
(Williams 1930)

‘“Three trees are good in type
Holly and Ivy and Yew
Which bear leaves while alive
I am Trystan's while he lives.”’
(Rowland 2019: 60)

This rhyming quatrain is not one of the linguistically interesting early *englynion* (Rowland and Thomas 1982) but is interesting in that it presumes knowledge of the distinction between deciduous and evergreen plants. It is the disruptive nature of the evergreen plants here which allows Esyllt to circumvent Arthur's ruling and escape her loveless marriage. Interestingly, the other conifers sometimes also have a superficially similar disruptive function in medieval Welsh texts. This passage in particular makes a useful comparison to a much earlier Arthurian romance. In *Owein*, or *Iarlles y Ffynnon*, as well as *Yvain*, the Old French version of the story, one of the most important settings of the text is the titular fountain (sometimes also translated as a well or spring). This fountain is returned to regularly by various knights over the course of the tale because it can be used to produce storms and to summon each other into single combat. This seemingly disruptive act actually provides a structure to the text, and the fountain becomes a place for young men to test their masculinity and (theoretically) gain a knightly education and a sense of moderation (cf. Roberts 1987; Urban 2009; Scott 2009). The fountain does not stand alone in the landscape:

'Ac odyno ti a wely ystrat megys dyffryn mawr, ac ympherued yr ystrat y gwely pren mawr a glassach y vric no'r fenitwyd glassaf. Ac y dan y pren hwnnw y mae fynhawn, ac yn emhyl y fynhawn y mae llech wawr [Red Book: varmor], ac ar y llech y mae kawc aryant wrth kadwyn aryant mal na ellir y gwahanu.' (Thomson 1968: 7)

'“And from there you will see a broad river valley, like a wide vale, and in the middle of the valley you will see a great tree, its branches greener than the greenest fir trees. And under that tree there is a well, and near the well there is a marble slab, and on the slab there is a silver bowl fastened to a silver chain so that they cannot be separated.”' (Davies 2007: 119)

The idyllic scene being described here is a motif which also occurs in Old French and Middle English literature. In *Yvain*, the twelfth-century Old French version of the Arthurian legend by Chretien de Troyes, the tree at the fountain beside the basin and the slab is expressly called a *pin* ('pine') all the way through the text, and is said to be beautiful and evergreen: *An toz tans la fuelle li dure / Qu'il ne la pert por nul iver* (Reid and Foerster 1942: 384–5) ('Its leaves stay on in all seasons; it doesn't lose them in even the harshest winter' (Kibler and Carroll 1991: 299–300)). In the Old French and Middle English *Le Roman de la Rose/The Romaunt of the Rose*, a fountain is again described with a marble slab under an exceptionally tall and beautiful pine (Sutherland 1967: ll. 1425–32 and 1455–62). Based on beautiful scenes like this, Carole Hough (2003) argues that pine trees generally have a romantic significance in Middle English literature. There is also, however, something dangerous and disruptive about other examples of this motif. A good example of this is the appearance of the motif in the twelfth-century Anglo-Norman *Song of Roland*, although here the fountain is missing. In this virulently Islamophobic text the pine tree seems

to represent the French court and the forces of Christianity (Brault 1978: 68; Steinmeyer 1963). Charles, the Christian Emperor of France, regularly holds court under pine trees (Burgess 1990: 8, 11, 12)). The pine stands in contrast to the olive tree which represents Muslim Spain (Vos 1974). The space under pine was also seen as appropriate for last stands. When Ganelon of France is nearly attacked at the council of Marsile, the Muslim King of Spain, he draws his sword and puts his back to a pine tree (Burgess 1990: 37). When the Twelve Peers of France prepare for a rear-guard battle, they arm themselves under a grove of pines (78). And finally when Roland, the titular character, realises he is going to die he literally runs to be under a pine tree (*pin*) once again (174), before lying down to die underneath it (176). For this scene in particular, the pine tree may also be an allusion to the cross, with Roland sacrificing his life for his beliefs just like Jesus did (Brault 1978: 69). This particular pine tree is described earlier in the story:

Devers Espaigne een vai en un guarét
Muntet sur un tertre desuz un arbre bel,
Quatre perruns i ad de marbre faiz.

‘He goes over towards Spain, into a fallow field;
He climbs on to a mound, beneath a beautiful tree.
Four great marble blocks are there.’ (Burgess 1990: 168)

For medieval authors, the conifers were not just disruptive in that the dramatic moments of the texts happened underneath them; Welsh and English authors sometimes seem to have considered them so disruptive to texts that they needed to be removed. While in the Old French and Anglo Norman *Yvain, Le Roman de la Rose* and *The Song of Roland* there are literal pine trees, in *Owein* the species of this tree itself is never specified; we only know that its colour is like that of a fir tree. Where clarity is needed it is occasionally afterwards called *y prenn glas* (‘the green tree’), referring back to this passage (Thomson 1968: 11, 18). The Middle English *Yvain and Gawain* also changes the species, here making the tree a hawthorn rather than a conifer at all (Braswell 1995: 353; 627). Similarly, while the tree remains a pine in the Middle English *Romaunt of the Rose*, the author seems to draw some cultural distance from it in the comment: *Whiche tree in Fraunce men cal a pyne* (Sutherland 1967: 1457). In *Cân Rolant*, the Middle Welsh translation of the *Song of Roland*, the pine trees are again omitted. In one manuscript (NLW MS Peniarth 10, verse XXV), what was a pine tree is even turned into an *wmbyr* tree (a misunderstanding of the Anglo Norman word *umbre* meaning ‘shadow’ (Rejhon 1984: 65)), which might suggest that the translator had difficulty even understanding the word *pin* (‘pine’). These changes can be understood to be a product of a *translatio* from one culture to another (Roberts 1987; Poppe 2004; Reck 2019). The same process can be seen in the change of the camels and bears in the *Song of Roland* into the horses and roe deer of *Cân Rolant* and the omission of the Breton Forest of Brocéliande between *Yvain* and *Owein* (although it is contrary to the retention of Norman loanwords in descriptions of the outfits in *Owein*, and the retention

of the Olive trees in *Can Rolant* (Cordo Russo 2014a: 175, 206–7; Cordo Russo 2014b). The most probable explanation for the change in how the pine trees are depicted is that the inclusion of pine trees established a less familiar setting for Middle English and Middle Welsh authors and audiences. The very mention of the extinct Scots Pine might have disrupted the ability of readers to imagine the story, despite the apparently strong cultural currency of terms like *pinus* and *ffynidwydd*.

In some medieval stories, conifers are also disruptive in that they mark the borders of an Otherworldly realm. In the fourteenth-century Middle English *Confessio Amantis*, the edge of the domain of Pan is *enclosed with the tres of Pigne* (Macaulay 1901: V.1005–19). The association between Otherworldly figures and conifers is also seen in medieval Irish literature, so for example the final trysting place of Cuchulainn and Fand in *The Wasting Sickness of Cúchulainn* is *Ibor Cind Tráchtá* (Newry – literally ‘the Yew Tree at the Head of the Strand’) (Gantz 1981: 174); interestingly, this is the same place where yew trees were recorded as being burned in *The Annals of the Four Masters* in 1162. When Cuchulainn is seeking training from Scáthach and permission to marry her daughter in *The Wooing of Emer*, he is advised to ambush her under another yew tree (Meyer 1888: 300). A much later parallel in Welsh literature might be the fifteenth-century poetry of Dafydd ab Edmwnd, in the *Kowydd a wnaeth ef i’r ywen* (‘The *cywydd* he made to the yew tree’), where the poet explains how he set out on the feast of St John (on 24 June, close to the summer solstice) to Dafydd ap Gwilym’s yew tree. Here again the yew tree is a trysting spot, with perhaps some supernatural properties: *ir ywenn awn inau’r nos / yno vnawr yw nownos* (Roberts 1914: 11.13–14) (‘I went to the yew for the night / there one hour is nine nights’). This sense of liminality may also be intended by the comparison to fir in the thirteenth- or fourteenth-century Middle Welsh *Breuddwyd Rhonabwy* (‘The Dream of Rhonabwy’). This scene, describing Iddog Cordd Prydain, comes immediately after Rhonabwy falls into the dream world of the text. In this context, the mention of the fir, along with the weird, unnatural colours and the giant size of the knights might function as a sign to the reader that the story is now continuing within a dream (Zhao 2021: 80; Davies 1997: 133):

Sef y gwelei gwraenc penngrych melyn a’e varyf yn newyd eillaw,
y ar varch melyn. Ac o penn y dwygoes a thal y deulin y waeret yn
las. A pheis o bali melyn am y marchawc, wedy ry wniaw ac adauw
glas. A chledyf eurdwrn ar y glun, a gwein o gordwal newyd idaw,
a charrei o ledyr ewic a gwaec erni o eur. Ac ar warthaf hynny llen
o pali melyn wedy ry wniaw a sidan glas, a godreon y llenn [yn]
las, ac a oed las o wisc y marchawc a’e uarch a oed kyn lasset a
deil y ffenitwyd, ac a oed velyn ohonei a oed kyn uelynet a blodeu
y banadyl. (Richards 1948: 4)

‘Here he saw a young man with curly blond hair and a newly trimmed beard. He was on a yellow horse, and from the top of its forelegs and the ends of its knees down was green. And the knight had a tunic of yellow brocaded silk which had been embroidered

with green thread. And there was gold-hilted sword on his thigh, and it had a sheath of new Cordovan leather, and a thong of hind's leather with a clasp of gold. And over that a mantle of yellow brocaded silk which had been embroidered with green silk, and the edges of the mantle were green, and that which was green of the outfit of the knight and his horse was as green as the needles of fir trees, and that which was yellow of it was as yellow as the flowers of broom.' (my translation)

In medieval Welsh literature, people are often described and characterised by the colour of their hair, so that blond women might be beautiful virgins or evil seductresses, and blond men might be strong warriors or handsome nobles (Hopwood 2016: 22–31; 210–18; Davies 1988). In more intricate descriptions, comparisons are often drawn between the colour of a person's hair and a plant, so that, for example, authors regularly highlighted women as beautiful by comparing their hair to the flowers of broom (Bromwich 2014: 488; Hopwood 2016: 39–41; Davies 1995: 148–58). At first glance, the description of Iddog Cordd Prydain provided in *Breuddwyd Rhonabwy* fits with this theme – his hair, like that of other characters in *Rhonabwy*, is yellow as the broom, which might characterise him as beautiful, strong and noble. However, the striking green and yellow outfit that Iddog wears is not traditional. In the medieval period, the colour term *glas* (now normally 'blue') is not normally applied to human clothing, but it was commonly used to describe the colour of plants and leaves, so for example *glas kelyn* ('holly is green' – Haycock 2007: 3.135); *glas cunlleit* ('herbage is green' – Jacobs 2012: 1.35); *dail glas ar dâl y glyn* ('green leaves at the head of the valley' – Lake et al. 2007: 36.25). This is interesting because, in contrast, *gwyrdd* ('green') seems to be an especially attractive colour for human clothing in medieval poetry (Lake et al. 2007: 138.6; Edwards 2006: 3.88). The description of the knight in *Breudwyt Rhonabwy* is also much more intricate than is typical from other medieval Welsh prose literature (Davies 1995: 153–6; Davies 1997: 132–4; Davies 1988). The colophon at the end hints that the text has been purposefully made complicated in terms of the number of colours and the unusual choice of colours in order to make memorisation more difficult (Richards 1948: 21). This suggests that scholarship (Giffin 1958; Jones 2007: 99–100) attempting to explain the descriptions in *Breuddwyd Rhonabwy* by drawing parallels with historical descriptions of outfits and battles might be misplaced. The colours in *Breuddwyd Rhonabwy* were intended to be excessive rather than realistic in order to parody traditional storytelling conventions (Bollard 1981; Lloyd-Morgan 1991). The description of the colour of the fir tree in this text, just like in *Owein* and *Trystan and Esyllt*, has a disruptive purpose: Iddog Cord Prydain is described in excessive detail and seems to be wearing a colour only normally seen in plants.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper has been to examine the three conifers which are regularly described in medieval Welsh sources. The term *yw* refers to the yew. Yew trees were, and are, commonly present outside churches, abbeys and at holy wells, and must have stood out in the later medieval period, when they became rarer as demand rose for yew bows. The term *pinus* refers to the pine tree. Scots Pines were almost extinct in the south of Britain at this time, but some populations are known to have survived into the medieval period, and the medieval references in *Y Gododdin* and possibly *Eiry Mynyd* and others might refer to remnant populations of pine trees. The term *ffynidwydd* can be translated as 'fir' in the broadest sense. It is likely that this term sometimes also referred to populations of Scots pine, as for example in *Cad Goddeu*. Each of the conifers had a particular reputation in medieval Welsh literature. Fir trees were especially known for their aromatic wood. Pine and yew trees had a reputation for being holy. Yew had this reputation because of the presence of holy yew trees, most famously including the one at Dafydd ap Gwilym's grave at Strata Florida described by Gruffudd Gryg. Pine had a comparable reputation for holiness because it was thought of as the wood of the cross, based on the legend of the rood, most famously told in *Ystoria Adaf*. In addition to this, references to conifers also sometimes act to disrupt medieval Welsh texts. This can be in terms of their evergreen colour as in the later reference to yew in *Trystan and Esyllt*, or the references to fir in *Breudwyt Rhonabwy* and *Owein*. The motif of the fountain under the green tree in *Owein* also appears in Middle English and Old French literature where it seems to function as a dramatic setting for the most important moments of the text. As part of this depiction, conifers sometimes seem to mark the boundaries of Otherworldly realms.

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